

**SUBJECT: THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL BASIS
OF DEVELOPING IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY AGAINST RELIGIOUS
FAITH**

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Abstract: Today, the role of mature, highly spiritual young people in our rapidly developing motherland is extremely important. In this article, the pedagogical foundations of the development of ideological immunity against religious fanaticism are theoretically analyzed, and the role of a healthy environment in the coming of age of the young generation is important. is explained.

Key words: National idea, national ideology, ideological immunity, religion, religious fanaticism, education, religious extremism.

Since ancient times, representatives of several nationalities and peoples have lived peacefully in our motherland Uzbekistan. Many of them believed in different religions. Representatives of our nation have always treated representatives of other religions with respect. Even today, the policy of religious tolerance is being carried out in our country. However, there are forces that threaten peace in the society. Cases of religious intolerance and Islamophobia, which have recently been observed in some countries, cannot be allowed. Therefore, in order to prevent the spread of the scourge of extremism and the radicalization of young people, it is necessary to strengthen joint efforts¹.

At this point, we must first of all pay special attention to the concepts of religious extremism and ideological immunity.

Religious fanaticism is a system of actions in which a person zealously defends his religious ideas and views.

Religious fanaticism is one of the possible forms or stages of the development of religion conditioned by the functioning of religion as a special social institution or subsystem in the social system.

Religious extremism is the ideology and activities of some religious organizations or mainly some religious people that do not correspond to the rules of society.

¹Mirziyoyev SH,M. “Speech at the 78th session of the United Nations General Assembly”

Ideological immunity is a system of ideological views and values that serve to protect an individual, social group, nation, society from various harmful ideological influences. Immunity (Latin *immunitas* - release, escape) is a medical concept, it is understood as a set of reactions capable of maintaining the permanent internal identity of the organism, protecting itself from various influences and external infections².

In order to be able to resist any religious currents (be it terrorist or extremist) in the society, a person must first of all develop ideological immunity, which is a system of ideological and theoretical views and values. Because today there are no forces around us that threaten our country by masking religion. "Today it is necessary to protect our religion, it is necessary to protect believers and Muslims. But, first of all, we need to protect our religion from these evil forces who claim to be "true Muslims", bloodthirsty and murderers who use the word "jihad" every step of the way and commit corruption in the name of religion³. Today, the democratic changes taking place in our country require us to be more attentive than ever, to inculcate only creative ideas in the minds of our youth.

It should not be forgotten that currently there are many political forces and movements that are trying to expand their sphere of influence through ideological means. Hegemony, aggressive nationalism and chauvinism, racism and religious extremism

ideologies are among them. In order to inculcate the ideology of independence in people's hearts and minds, it is necessary to cover all spheres of society's life, to use effective methods and tools of education, promotion and propaganda⁴. In order to prevent this, we must educate young people in the spirit of preserving our values, customs and traditions inherited from the past. Because it is important to learn a deep lesson from the past and preserve our national heritage for future generations. A free and prosperous society is the guarantee of our great future.

Also, the harmony of religious and worldly values, the educational influence of the environment in the family and society are of incomparable importance in educating the future generation in the spirit of humanity. Religious values, which are our spiritual heritage, formed by our ancestors for thousands of years and refined over centuries, help to expand the worldview of

² National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. First volume. Tashkent, 2000.

³ Karimov I. A., Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development, T., 1997.

⁴ Toychiyev B., Ergashev I., Mukhammadiyeva O.M., Khojayev M.I., National Idea: Development Strategy of Uzbekistan, Tashkent: "Innovatsiya-Ziya", 2020.- 56-p.

young people. By educating children in a harmony of worldly and religious values, a healthy faith is formed in practice, and it makes it possible to distinguish various heretical and superstitious practices, to create immunity against the influence and beliefs of different religious currents and directions. Religious fanaticism forces people to live according to certain rules, deprives people of freedom, and directs them to blindly confirm other religious beliefs and views⁵.

Fanaticism is established in people's minds based on certain pressures and eventually rises to the level of faith. Fanaticism can be manifested in two ways: worldly and religious. Examples of worldly fanaticism are chauvinism and egoism. Wahhabism and Hizbut-Tahrir al-Islami organization can be cited as an example of religious fanaticism. The purpose of the Hizb-Tahrir al-Islami organization is as follows:

starting a civil war in a peaceful country;

- disruption of the country's economic activity;
- creating inter-ethnic and inter-religious relations;
- bringing weapons and drugs into the country and endangering the peaceful life of citizens;
- dependence of an independent state on foreign countries producing weapons⁶;

It can be seen that fanaticism affects not only religion, but also worldly spheres. Because no matter what field a person is a representative of, in order not to blindly follow the events happening in the society, he should be immune to that event. For this reason, a person should not be limited to initial knowledge. The roots of religious fanaticism go back to the distant past. Because religious fanatics have existed in all periods of history.

One of the most famous fanatics of ancient times was Nero, the Roman dictator. Nero's belief was that power was dearer than anything else. His belief was that any means should be used to achieve and maintain power. At the same time, Nero, who lived by his own opinion, consistently followed his slogans to gain power. The saddest thing is that he sacrifices his loved ones in the path of this creed, including his own mother Agrippina. After coming to the top of the power, he kills people who oppose his ideas or express a critical opinion, regardless of who they are⁷.

⁵ Shermukhamedov K.A., Karimov J.A., Spiritual and educational foundations of the fight against extremism and terrorism, Tashkent: "National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2018. – 6-p.

⁶ Husniddinov Z. Islam: directions, sects, currents. - T.: 2000. – 47- p.

⁷ Abdullajonov O. "The origin, nature and introduction of religious fanaticism to Uzbekistan", Tashkent: "Akademiya" 2000. - 3-4 p.

Or, as another example, the massacre of many people as a result of the organized massacre of Protestants in France. It went down in history under the name “Bartholomew Night”.

It can be seen that religious fanaticism has existed since ancient times and it continues to this day. For this reason, today we must take measures to develop ideological immunity in the minds of our youth, which can resist any fanatical force.

Today, a person or his group who illegally fulfills his religious goal focuses his attention first of all on capturing and poisoning the minds of the youth, who are the present and future of our country. We must strengthen our control over our youth so that they do not fall into their clutches and try to fill their minds with creative ideas.

Religious bigotry (fanaticism) is the source of religious extremism. Bigotry is the result of people blindly believing in a certain thing, thought or idea, without reaching its deep essence, believing it to be more correct than all other things and ideas. Bigotry in society arises as a result of the following reasons:

- low standard of living of the population and insufficient development of social relations;
- insufficient development of religious knowledge and level of citizens, predominance of religious ignorance⁸;

Today, religious extremism and terrorism also threaten the development of society. Extremist and terrorist organizations of various appearances are attracting young people to their ranks.

Extremism and terrorism, if we look at their history, are mainly products of religious fundamentalism and fanaticism. Extremism and terrorism are both political and religious products. The causes of extremism and terrorism can be different. For example: intimidation of the population, social and political manipulation, creation of an atmosphere of panic and disorder, coercion, destabilization of society’s own rules, individuals and society; breaking the unity and integrity of society and the state, seizing power and establishing a new “theocratic” totalitarian regime⁹. One of the most urgent issues today is the formation of ideological immunity among citizens in the fight against terrorism

⁸ Narbekov A.V. Fundamentals of religious studies: Study guide. - T.: Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2008. - 216 p.

⁹ Petrov D. B. Prevention of religious extremism: theory and practice: educational and methodological manual. – Saratov: Publishing House “Saratov Source”, 2018. – 24-25 p.

and extremism, and at the same time, paying special attention to the education of young people.

If physical education makes a child physically strong, strong, and healthy, through spiritual education, qualities of high morality, goodness, humanity, courage, compassion, and hard work are formed in him. Spiritual education serves to preserve the child's identity and enrich his inner world. As the great scholar, our compatriot Abu Rayhan Beruni said, "Man is the highest breed, perfection of nature, the human race is higher than all animals. A great honor has been shown to man - he has been given intelligence. For this reason, in order for the spiritual world of a person to correspond to the tasks set before him, he must be highly moral, knowledgeable, and enlightened". Therefore, child education is first of all determined by the strength of its spiritual foundation. Therefore, in the formation of national identity, religious knowledge and worldview in young people, it is necessary to use modern literature, which contains both scientific and religious information, which can reveal the origin and true essence of every custom, ritual, tradition and our values. Achieving a positive result through activities such as providing, showing spiritual and educational programs is considered one of the important factors. Because such measures, in a certain sense, enrich the minds of young people, distinguish between real national and religious values and all kinds of heretical and superstitious practices, create immunity against the influence of various religious currents and trends, and the beliefs of extremist and terrorist groups. allows to do. From this point of view, it is important for young people to respect our national customs, traditions and rituals, to constantly explain their educational importance, to protect them from spiritual threats and to realize their identity¹⁰. The role of family, school and neighborhood is extremely important in the formation of ideological immunity. Because in order to fight against these evils, first of all, the environment around us, the mutual relations of the citizens in it, and their relations with each other should be put on the right track.

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¹⁰ Shermukhamedov K.A., Karimov J.A., Spiritual and educational foundations of the fight against extremism and terrorism, Tashkent: "National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2018. - 161 p.

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